

A Case Report on Left Side Loculated Pleural Effusion Tubercular and its Management

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Abstract: Tubercular pleural effusion is an abnormal accumulation of fluid in the lungs. Still, it is a cause for major developing in the areas of Asia nations, Western Europe and Africa. It is a complex condition due to fibrin deposition in the pleural space, caused by excessive fluid, either protein-poor (transudative) or protein-rich (exudative). Though the tubercular effusion typically exudative in nature clinical features of an include chest pain, cough, fever and breathlessness. Early diagnosis and anti tubercular therapy are essential to prevent complications such as pleural thickening, fibrosis and long term respiratory impairment

Keywords: tubercular, protein-poor, protein-rich, therapeutic

1. INTRODUCTION:

Tubercular pleural effusion occurs when excess fluid accumulates in the pleural space due to inflammation caused by the organism *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (MTB). MTB is a slender aerobic bacterium that does not absorb Gram stain. Loculated pleural effusion is a more serious form of pleural disease that is harder to find and treat. If not treated it in right way, it can make the illness last longer, stop the lungs from expanding properly, and cause serious problems like pleural thickening and cirrhosis. This can lead to chronic breathing problems that make your lung capacity smaller, make short of breath all the time, and lower quality of life [1,2,3]. When a loculated pleural effusion isn't treated, it can turn into a severe infection called empyema. This causes pus to form in the pleural space, which makes the infection spread faster and can cause sepsis and waiting too long to get help means being sick for longer, not getting enough food, and more people dying. If it get diagnosed and treated in early, these problems go away and person get better completely. Pleural effusion is the most common lung disease that doctors see all over the world. The causes of pleural effusion vary depending on where the person

1.1. PHARMACOEPIDEMOLOGY:

Tuberculosis is a very important risk factor for loculated pleural effusion because it causes long-term inflammation, which makes it harder to diagnose and treat, which can lead to very bad cases in patients, especially in developing countries like Southeast Asia and Africa. Which cause about 30–60% of pleural effusion cases. In India, however, tubercular effusion is the most common type, making up almost 40–50% of all exudative pleural effusions seen in clinical practice. Countries with low rates of TB, like North America and Western Europe, which made up less than 5–10% of pleural effusion cases. Most cases of TB occurred in young adults, age group of 20 to 40 years [4]. This is because of their immune systems are strong enough to cause pleural effusion, which can look like a reactivation of latent TB and is less likely to be linked to other health problems. Cases involving pediatric patients are infrequent; however, when they do arise, they may manifest in high-burden environments [5]. The gender distribution was which is known to be more male than female. The differences are due to higher risk,

work-related factors, smoking habits, and patterns of seeking health care. In recent years, better ways to diagnose problems have come about TB.

1.2. SIGNS AND SYMPTOMS:

People with loculated pleural effusion usually come in with both breathing problems and signs of an infection throughout the body. Chest pain, ongoing breathlessness, cough, and a low-grade fever that gets worse in the evenings are the main symptoms. They usually get worse over the course of weeks. Because of the inflammation that comes with TB, you might also notice that you lose weight, have no appetite, and feel generally tired.

1.3. PATHOGENESIS:

The pathogenesis of TB pleural effusion entails an immune-mediated inflammatory response characterized by the direct invasion of the pleural space by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. The antigens get to the pleura, which starts the delayed hypersensitivity reaction that T.Lymphocytes control. The immune system helps release inflammatory cytokines, which make the capillaries in the pleural membranes more permeable. If the inflammation keeps going, the fibrin will organize into fibrous strands and separate the pleural fluid into different compartments. This will cause the protein-rich fluid to build up in the pleural cavity space. This leads to the formation of loculate pleural effusion, which stops free fluid movement and makes it harder for the lungs to expand. If not treated, it keeps causing inflammation and could lead to pleural thickening and fibrosis, which would make breathing difficult for a long time. Early medical treatment will stop this bad process and stop damage to the pleura that can't be fixed. The detailed flow chart is given in Figure 1.

Fig.1. Pathogenesis of pleural effusion

1.4. ETIOLOGY:

There are many things that can cause left loculated pleural effusions. Parapneumonic effusions from pneumonia are the most common type, but if bacteria get in there, it can turn into empyema, which is a pus-filled mess. In some areas, tuberculosis likes the left side, which makes thick loculations that are hard to fix. Malignancy, such as lung cancer or metastasis, also results in bloody, viscous fluid accumulations on the left side. Heart failure can cause effusions, but loculation happens less often unless it joins in. Trauma, like an injury to the spleen, can cause bleeding that happens quickly. Infection-related: Recent studies show that pneumonia or TB is responsible for about 40% of cases. Cancer-linked: up to 20% come from tumors, which are often harder to get rid of.

1.4. CLINICAL FEATURES:

Some patients may exhibit clinical symptoms, including pleuritic chest pain confined to the affected side. People often complain of shortness of breath, which can range from mild to severe depending on how much the pleura is involved. There may be a persistent cough that is either dry or productive. People report systemic symptoms like low-grade fever (especially at night), night sweats, fatigue, loss of appetite, and weight loss. The physical exam showed that the chest wasn't expanding as much on the affected side, which is something that happens a lot. Breath sounds may be reduced in the vicinity of a pleural effusion. Percussion shows a dull note in the lung fields. In instances of considerable effusion or loculation, tachypnea and augmented respiratory effort may be observed. The general examination shows signs of a long-term illness, like pale skin and weight loss.

2. CASE REPORT:

2.1. PATIENT PROFILE: A 27-year-old patient who was a student presented to OPD with chief complaints of severe dry cough for 20 days and difficulty in breathing for 15 days, and the dry cough is not constant and is seasonal, and not had any throat pain as well as hemoptysis. According to the patient's physical assessment, mindful and shows the febrile condition at the time of admission, but the patient has repeatedly suffering from difficulty breathing for 15 days, which is noted as grade II. But the characteristics can be seen as including the orthopnea (difficulty in breathing when lying down) and PND/E (Paroxysmal Nocturnal Dyspnea), which is shortness of breath that occurs at night, though not always present; there is no reported seasonal or diurnal variation, and the condition is described as non-progressive. But the patient was showing low-grade fever with chills for one week, starting 20 days ago, which subsided with treatment. The patient is a student, and the diet is mixed. Negative history, no history of trauma, asthma, or previous TB contact.

2.2. Physical Examination:

The vitals are tachycardia (pulse: 108-112 bpm) and tachypnea (RR: 20-24 breaths/min).

Respiratory system:

Percussion: dullness noted over the left infra-mammary, axillary, and infra scapular regions.

Auscultation: which is diminished breath sounds (VBS) over the left lung zones.

3. DIAGNOSTIC ASSESSMENT:

3.1. Imaging & Laboratory Investigation

Chest x-ray: confirmed left-sided loculated pleural effusion. The pleural fluid analysis is ADA level of 354U/L, highly diagnostic for tuberculosis. diagnostic findings the patients pleural fluid analysis was a critical diagnostic factor . which was a high level of adenosine deamiase(ADA) was recorded (354U/L).According to established Emergency medicine criteria, an ADA level>50 U/L, which is particularly when accompanied by an exudative fluid and lymphocytic predominance. Which is the primary indicator of tuberculosis?

3.2. Laboratory trends:

WBC COUNT: his white blood cell count showed a downward trend from an initial 12,750 cells/cumm over four days, suggesting a positive response to treatment.

Blood Chemistry: The tests conducted on admission showed a blood urea of 16 mg/dl and serum creatinine of 0.6mg/dl.

Management: The patient was prescribed tab.Akurit-4(a standard four–drug anti–tubercular regimen) and Tab.Benadon (pyridoxine/VitaminB6) to prevent neurological side effects often associated with TB medication. Additionally, incentive spirometry was ordered to encourage lung re-expansion.

3.3. Differential Diagnosis Based On Pleural Fluid:

Medical professionals use specific criteria in pleural fluid analysis to distinguish between various underlying causes of fluid accumulation. The following table explains the diagnostic markers observed in the provided reference materials. The majority of medical has specific criteria for this diagnosis as his diagnosis of loculated of loculated pleural effusion, which is difficult to find its at an early stage of TB, as it is accompanied by exudative fluid and lymphocytic predominance, which is also a primary indicator of tuberculosis.

3.4. Imaging: chest x ray(CXR):

On the chest x-ray image, the primary finding is a large area of opacity (whiteness) in the lower two-thirds of the left lung, which obscures the normal lung structure and diaphragm on that side as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Posteroanterior (pa)view chest X-ray of a 27-year-old male

3.5. Key Radiographic Findings :

Loculated pleural effusion: The shape and distribution of the fluid collection suggest it is “trapped” or loculated rather than free flowing, which often happens with infection like tuberculosis.

Presence of an ICD tube: which we can clearly see is a curved intercostal chest drainage (ICD) tube inserted into the pleural space. This is used to drain fluid or air from the cavity.

Tracheal shift: the dark tube in the center of the neck appears slightly which is shifted towards the right, suggesting that the pressure from the fluid on the left side is pushing the central structures away.

3.6. Medical Thoracoscopy:

The visual findings are consistent with an angry type of inflammation

Fibrinous adhesions: the white, web-like or sheet-like structure stretching across the cavity is composed of fibrin strands. In TB, the intense inflammation causes the accumulation of fibrin, which acts like glue, sticking the visceral and parietal pleura together.

Loculation formations: these fibrin strands create physical barriers or walls. This is exactly how the loculated pleural effusion develops. Fluids become trapped in these newly formed pockets, making it impossible to drain with a simple needle aspiration

Pleural hyperemia: The intense, deep red color of the tissue indicates severe hyperemia, which increases blood flow and active inflammation of the pleural lining.

Sago-like nodules: if we look closely at the red-like appearances, which are tiny, pale, grain like elevations. In a tubercular case, these are often pleural tubercles, which are small granulomas where the mycobacterium tuberculosis located which is shown in Figure 3.

Fig.3: Thoracoscopic view of the pleural space revealing pleural hyperemia and extensive fibrinous adhesions (loculations) characteristic of tubercular pleurisy

3.7. Clinical Correlation:

Difficulty in drainage: the ICD tube might not achieve complete drainage immediately. The walls seen here require either fibrinolytic agents like streptokinase or VATS (video –assisted thoracoscopic surgery) to break them down [6].

Diagnostic gold standard: if a biopsy was taken during this procedure, it would likely confirm the diagnosis by showing caseation granulomas or through a positive AFB (acid-fast bacilli) culture is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Diagnostic gold standard criteria

Condition	Primary Diagnostic Criteria
Tuberculosis	Which is characterized by exudative fluid and high lymphocyte counts, and ADA levels exceeding 50U/L
Empyema	by the presence of pus, positive gram stains, elevated LDH(>1000) and low glucose /ph levels
Malignancy	Indicated by exudative fluid with lymphocytic predominance and positive results from cytology(cell testing)
Hemothorax	Diagnosed when the haematocrit of the pleural effusion is more than 50% of the haematocrit of the blood.
Chylothorax	Confirmed by elevated triglycerides (>110mg/dl) and the presence of the chylomicrons.
Fungal infection	Suspected if the fluid is black-colored and which is confirmed via fungal smears or culture.

3.8. **Management:** Core Treatment :anti-tubercular therapy(ATT) is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Core Treatment

Category	Brand Medication	Dose/Frequency	Mechanism of Action
Anti-tubercular (ATT)	Akurit-4 (Rifampicin, Isoniazid, Ethambutol Pyrazinamide)	3 tablets/OD	Inhibits bacterial RNA synthesis, cell wall assembly, and membrane potential
Neuroprotection	Tab.benadon(pyridoxine /vitB6)	40mg/OD	Acts as a coenzyme to prevent peripheral neuropathy caused by isoniazid
Respiratory adjuvant	Tab.Montelukast LC	1 Tablet/HS	Antagonizes leukotriene receptors to reduce airway inflammation & edema
Nutritional support	Tab.orofer XT(iron folic acid)	1 Tablet/OD	Provides essential iron & folate for erythropoiesis

4. CURRENT SURGICAL & PROCEDURAL THERAPY:

4.1. Intercostal drainage(ICD):

Procedure: a left-sided chest tube was inserted to facilitate fluid evacuation

Monitoring: Clinicians monitored for column movement and air leaks to ensure system patency.

Outcome: the cumulative output reached approximately 1700ml of exudative fluid following fibrinolytic administration.

Thoracentesis: used initially to aspirate fluid for biochemical analysis, which revealed a pathognomonic ADA in U/L 354ml.

4.2. Supportive acute therapy:

Which is used to control symptoms and secondary infections during the hospital stay, the medication history is given in Table 3.

Table 3. Current treatment

Brand medication	Dose/frequency	Mechanism of action
Inj.zostrum(cefuroxime)	1.5g/IV/BD	Second generation cephalosporin that inhibits bacterial cell wall synthesis.
Inj. Clindamycin	600mg/IV/BD	lincosamide antibiotic that stops bacteria from making proteins at the 50s ribosome
Inj.pantop(pantoprazole)	40mg/IV/OD	Irreversibly inhibits the proton pump(H^+/k^+ -atpase)to reduce gastric acid
Inj.dynapar(diclofenac)	1AMPin 100mlNS/BD	Inhibits cyclooxygenase (cox) enzyme to reduce pain-inducing prostaglandins

4.3. Post-procedural rehabilitation:

The treatment was not limited to medications but induced active physical recovery.

Incentive spirometry: performed hourly to encourage deep inspiration.

Purpose: which to promote the lung re-expansion and prevent atelectasis (lung collapse) after the fluid removal.

Table 4. Overall summary

Intervention	Brand/dose/frequency	Key role
Anti-tubercular (ATT)	Akurit-4(Rifampicin, Isoniazid, Pyrazinamide) /3tabs /OD	Eradicate M.tuberculosis
Fibrinolytic	Streptokinase/multiple doses	Lysing pleural loculations
Antibiotic	Zostum(1.5g)/IV/BD	Prevent secondary infection
Surgical	ICD tube/continuous	Mechanical fluid evacuation
Rehab	Spirometry/hourly	Restore lung volume

4.4. Patient Counselling:

Managing side effects and monitoring:

Expected changes rifampicin in akurit-4 will turn your urine, sweat, and tears an orange-red color. This is harmless and expected. Warning signs which are to contact the doctor immediately if you notice any yellowing of the eye/skin(jaundice), persistent nausea or severe abdominal pain, as these may indicate liver stress. By monitoring regularly the blood tests, the LFT, and WBC counts you had in the hospital will be required to ensure the body is tolerating the medication well.

4.5. Lifestyle and nutrition:

Diet: A high protein diet is recommend to aid tissue repair. Continue taking your tab oroferXT and haemcom sachets as prescribed to maintain your iron and nutritional levels during recovery.

Infection control: Ensuring your living space is well ventilated, while the pleural TB is generally less contagious than pulmonary TB, practicing good cough etiquette remains a healthy habit.

5. CONCLUSION:

THERAPEUTIC SUMMARY:

The patient's recovery was the result of a coordinated multimodal treatment strategy:

Surgical intervention: the placement of a left-sided intercostal drainage tube allowed for the mechanical evacuation of approximately 1700ml of exudative fluid.

Fibrinolytic therapy: The use of intrapleural streptokinase (STK) was essential to lyse the fibrin loculations that initially prevented effective drainage.

The clinical complexity of treating a 27-year old male student diagnosed with a left-sided loculated tubercular pleural effusion. The primary diagnostic breakthrough was achieved through pleural fluid analysis, which revealed a significantly elevated ADA level of 354U/L, a pathognomonic marker for tuberculosis in high-prevalence regions.

Final clinical outlook:

By the conclusion of the acute phase the patients vitals had been stabilized (Pulse:100bpm;RR:18-20 (breaths/min) and inflammatory markers(wbc:7300 cells/cumm) showed significant resolution .this case underscores that for loculated tubercular effusions a combination of chemical fibrinolysis and early mechanical drainage is a highly effective , nonsurgical alternative to invasive decortication ensuring a positive functional outcome for the patient.

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